

CESAER

Advancing innovation and knowledge valorisation from European Innovation Council

Position dated 13 December 2022

The leading universities of Science and Technology (S&T) united within [CESAER](#) welcome the focus at the European level on advancing innovation and knowledge valorisation, including as exemplified by the European Parliament's [report](#) on the implementation of the European Innovation Council (EIC), and the recommendation on guiding principles for knowledge valorisation and the conclusions on the European Innovation Agenda [adopted](#) by the Council of the EU on 2 December.

Entrepreneurs and innovators engaging in start-ups and scale-ups – especially in 'deep-tech' which is based on pushing boundaries in scientific knowledge and technology – are often students, researchers and university professionals. Therefore universities of S&T frequently have crucial and unique roles, and our association and Members are committed to [boosting disruptive innovation](#) and its [ecosystems](#), including through the [co-creation](#) of the code of practice for the smart use of intellectual property and by facilitating industry-academia engagements such as through [balancing](#) openness with commercialisation. Knowledge valorisation is most effective when universities can act autonomously and deploy physical, human and monetary assets in an agile way to support the development of an ecosystem as shown in our [white paper](#).

We have noted with concern that the model grant agreement for Horizon Europe introduces “additional IPR, dissemination and exploitation obligations” for EIC actions that diverge from standard practices used in other parts of the model grant agreement and are not aligned with best practices in knowledge transfer and valorisation, as outlined in detail in a [joint statement](#).

- We welcome and reinforce the [joint statement](#), and call upon the European Commission to harmonise the IP provisions related to EIC in the model grant agreement for Horizon Europe to align with current best practice.

We offer our expertise and to work together with the broader community and the European Commission on the swift follow-up to advance innovation and knowledge valorisation.

For more information and enquiries, please [contact](#) our Advisor for Innovation & Sustainability Louise Drogoul.

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